

COMPETENCE OF THE EDUCATIONIST, A MAJOR TREND IMPACTING EDUCATION

¹Ogbonna Nnamuchi, ²Amaka Nnamuchi

¹Faculty of Physical/Natural Sciences, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, P.M.B 02 Uli, Anambra State, Nigeria

²Faculty of Biological/Natural Sciences, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, P.M.B 02 Uli, Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract: A specialized definition of change would mean to change the traditional way such as that of an industry whose products are her graduates, especially in a new and effective way such as disruptive technology. Thus, competence of the educationist requires a high level of competency. This is where the price is paid for the crown won at last. As the Chief educationist who knows his weight aright, Henry bemoaned his position as king. The purposes of education that are accepted and the procedures used by a nation's leaders in implementing their educational programs may promote enlightenment and progress for all citizens or may perpetuate ignorance and misery or generate dangerous biases for many. In this paper the researcher explores factors necessary for sustainability of competence in the global educational system.

Keywords: Competence, Educationist, Education, Technology, disruptive, Transformative.

1. INTRODUCTION

Disruption is just as someone could be described as a noisy, disruptive influence in a group of other students. However, as education is business (either of an individual or government), a specialized definition of change would mean to change the traditional way such as that of an industry whose products are her graduates, especially in a new and effective way such as disruptive technology [6].

Having defined these important terms, we proceed further by taking onward journey into the following essential factors: Who is an educationist? The answer is not far-fetched. An educationist is a person who has a special knowledge of the principles and methods of teaching. For instance: Teachers, Lecturers, Rectors, Provosts, Housemistresses, etc. The counterpart question is equally necessary in dealing holistically with this topic, and that is:

What is Competence? Again, the answer is not still far-fetched. Competence is the ability to do something well [7]. It is a highly desired trait of the 21st Century educationist. The reverse is incompetence. Education has tremendous potential for good or for evil. The purposes of education that are accepted and the procedures used by a nation's leaders in implementing the program may promote enlightenment and progress for all citizens or may perpetuate ignorance and misery or generate dangerous biases for many. This has therefore now created this one or more problems faced by nations and in principle the educationists that attempt to develop an adequate plan and program for education [13]. One of the unique features of the organization and administration of education found in the United States is that Americans believe that those who are responsible (Educationists) for the administration of their schools (be they private or public governmental), as well as those who teach in the schools should be especially prepared to meet their responsibilities [8]. Sadly, this idea that educational administrators should have special preparation has developed slowly but is now accepted in practically all states. It has been highlighted that Outside of the country of America and a few others, the concept of special preparation for administrators has had comparatively little recognition or acceptance. This calls for adjustment action on the part of the global education administrators.

Thus competence of the educationist requires a high level of competency [14]. This is where the price is paid for the crown won at last. As the Chief educationist who knows his weight aright, Henry bemoaned his position as king in that he, unlike even the most humble cabin - boy, could not find moment's peace and repose. He conscientiously admitted: "*And in the visitation of the winds, who take then ruffian billows by the top, Curling their monstrous heads and hanging them with deafening clamour in the slippery clouds, That, with the hurly, death itself awakes? Canst thou, O partial sleep, give repose To the wet sea-boy in an hour so rude, And in the calmest and most stillest night, With all appliances and means to boot, Deny it to the king? Then happy low, lie down! Uneasy lies the head that wears a crown.*" Shakespeare's *Henry IV. Part II*, 1597.

Indeed Uneasy lies the head that wears the crown! Many educationist want to wear the crown without first paying the price. The educational leader must ensure he/she disrupts incompetence in her educational setting or be ready churn out 'cabin - boys' who with ease adorn with the educationist' crown.

1.1 Major changes needed to disrupt Incompetency

The following are recommended for the disruption of incompetency in educational setting:

- (i) Conduct regular Staff efficiency check and monitor educationist's efficiency level
- (ii) Term all educationists as potential and interview all educationists' before employing them
- (iii) Follow up with Regularization Assessment in case of infiltrations
- (iv) Pursue adherence to institutional goals, and entrenchment of same in the educationists
- (v) Monitoring and Supervision of the educationists' compliance to curriculum and quality assessment.

1.2. Role and responsibility of an educational leader with Major Considerations to ensure the recommended changes:

- (i) Competency training consisting of one or more skills whose mastery would enable the attainment of the competency.
- (ii) Link competency to all three of the domains under which performance can be assessed: They are knowledge, skills and attitude.
- (iii) Check for enduement with and Possession of a performance dimension, competencies are observable and demonstrable. Those who possess it will show this characteristics. [9]

1.3 Major Considerations of the Educational Leader to ensure intended Impact

Following Shemlev [11], a competency is more than just knowledge and skills; it involves the ability to meet complex demands by drawing on and mobilizing psychosocial resources (including skills and attitudes) in a particular context. The educationist need a wide range of competencies in order to face the complex challenges of today's world. Teaching competency is an inherent element of an effective training process. The central figures in the educational process are teachers, therefore the success of training and education depends on their preparation, erudition and performance quality. Therefore the educational leader must ensure that all their educationists demonstrate the following [10]:

- (i) Ability to perform complex pedagogical duties; to be well-spoken, in good mental and physical health, stable and tolerant;
- (ii) Have a propensity to work with the younger generation, good communicative and observational skills, tact, a vivid imagination, and leadership (iii) The educational leader has the responsibility to monitor the professional careers of their educationists, and to ensure they pass through the following levels of professional growth to achieve the acme of professional competency.
 - (a) 1st level: pedagogical ability – characterized by detailed knowledge of the subject;
 - (b) 2nd level: pedagogical skill – perfected teaching skill;
 - (c) 3rd level: pedagogical creativity – marked by implementation of new methods and techniques into educational activities;
 - (d) 4th level: pedagogical innovation – distinguished by the incorporation of essentially new, progressive theoretical ideas, principles and methods of training and education [12]

1.4 Action Plan

- Lay Emphasis on the preparation, selection, and role of administrators in relation to teaching and learning and to the operation of the instructional staff
- Pursue educational objectives by proper follow on individual educationist's assessment, sincerely and holistically drive to conclusive realization.
- Be hard (implement recommended disciplinary procedures), and where so recommended, lay off those who think business as usual, and has refused to improve or make changes.

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